

Chemistry–A European Journal

Supporting Information

Crystal Plane-Related Oxygen-Evolution Activity of Single Hexagonal Co_3O_4 Spinel Particles

Swapnil Varhade, Emmanuel Batsa Tetteh, Sascha Saddeler, Simon Schumacher, Harshitha Barike Aiyappa, Georg Bendt, Stephan Schulz, Corina Andronescu,* and Wolfgang Schuhmann*

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Section 1. Synthesis of Co_3O_4 hexagonal platelets

Figure S1: SEM micrographs of hexagonal Co_3O_4 particles deposited on a glassy carbon plate before and after dispersion in toluene.

Section 2. Substrate preparation

A glassy carbon plate was cleaned with diamond suspension with particle sizes of 0.05 μm , 0.3 μm , 1 μm . The plate was polished for 3-4 min with each particle size. After the plate was cleaned with ethanol and water, it is analyzed with SEM to check whether contaminations from the diamond suspensions are left over. Oleylamine-capped $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ hexagonal platelets were first dispersed in toluene solution and then ultrasonicated for 15 min. This sonicated solution is then drop-casted on the cleaned glassy carbon plate and dried under air for 15 min. The drop-coated glassy carbon plate is heated at 200 $^\circ\text{C}$ to remove the oleylamine surfactant and to convert the $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ to Co_3O_4 spinel (Figure S2 and S3). The oleylamine removal is verified using XPS and it was found that traces of carbon remain on the sample visible in the peak at 285 eV (C-C).^[1] However, according to the survey spectra the carbon is only present in traces which do not affect the catalytic performance.

Figure S2: Schematic illustration of the modification of the glassy carbon substrate with $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ containing dispersion.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Figure S3: a) XPS spectra of hexagonal shaped Co_3O_4 after annealing at 200 °C for 2 h along with Co 2p, O 1s, C 1s. b) Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern of hexagonal shaped Co_3O_4 after annealing at 200 °C for 2 h (gray), the calculated pattern (red), and the difference after subtraction (blue)

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Section 3. Capillary preparation

Double-barrel capillary: A quartz theta capillary is used as nanopipette for the experiment. The capillary surface is cleaned with isopropanol, and laser assisted pulling was done by means of a laser puller (P-2000, Sutter Instruments). A two-line program was used: Line 1: Heat 800, Filament 4, Velocity 40, Delay 130, Pull 0, Line 2: Heat 750-770, Filament 3, Velocity 30, Delay 130, Pull 70-90. To furnish hydrophobicity to the outer wall of capillary at the tip, the capillary end was dipped in dichlorodimethyl silane solution for 30 s simultaneously applying 6.5 bar of Ar pressure from the back end of the capillary. While keeping the Ar pressure from the back, the capillary is dried in air for 1 min to avoid insertion of silane solution inside the capillary (Figure S4a). The used capillaries possessed diameters of 500 nm – 1 μm (Figure S4b). Platinum wire of 0.25 mm diameter was used as quasi-reference counter electrodes. These wires were flame heated, then dipped in aqua regia for 4-5 s and washed with distilled water to remove possible surface impurities. The capillary was then filled with a solution containing 0.1 mM [(Os (2, 2'-bipyridine)₂(N, N'-dimethyl-2, 2'-biimidazole))(PF₆)₃] in 50 mM KOH using a MicroFil needle with 0.1 mm inner diameter (MF34G-5, World Precision Instruments). A thin layer of silicone oil was filled on-top to avoid evaporation of solution. Once the capillary is filled, the QRCEs were inserted in each barrel (Figure S4). A cyclic voltammogram of an Ohmic resistor was expected between the two QRCEs in the potential range from -50 to 50 mV (scan rate 50 mV/s).

Single barrel capillary: A quartz capillary is pulled using a laser puller (P-2000, Sutter Instruments, USA) to obtain the nanopipettes used in the SECCM experiments. A one-line program was used with the following parameters: Heat 730-780, Filament 3, Velocity 30, Delay 130, Pull 80-100. The so obtained capillaries possessed a diameter in between 500 nm – 1 μm (Figure S4c). A platinum wire with a diameter 0.25 mm was used as quasi-reference counter electrode and inserted from the back.

Figure S4: a) Schematic illustration of capillary preparation before SECCM experiments. b) SEM micrographs of one of the double-barrel capillaries (scale bar: 1 μm). c) SEM micrograph of one of the single-barrel capillaries (scale bar: 1 μm)

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Section 4. SECCM experiments

The use of the double- and single-barrel capillary is almost similar. The single barrel capillary is used when the substrate is conductive whereas double barrel capillary is used irrespective of the nature of the substrate because of an AC signal as feedback stop criterium.

Positioning: Using optical microscopy, the filled capillary is placed very close to the sample (Figure S5a). Once the approximate positioning of the capillary is done, the substrate is moved closer to the droplet meniscus at a rate of $0.4 \mu\text{m/s}$ with the help of the piezo nanocube. During the approach, a potential of 0.02 V is applied between the barrels so that a constant ionic current flows through the meniscus.

Approach: While approaching, the capillary is oscillated sinusoidally normal to the substrate with an amplitude of 38 nm and a frequency of 70 Hz . The alternating current component between the barrels is used as feedback signal to stop the approach of the substrate toward the capillary. Different feedback thresholds of 5 mV or 6 mV were used to stop the approach for different scans. For single-barrel capillary experiment, a current threshold of $4\text{--}5 \text{ pA}$ more than the background current signal was used as stop criterium.

SECCM Measurement: Once the testing of the approach is done, a scan was made across a $100 \mu\text{m} \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ area using the hopping mechanism mode. Four cyclic voltammograms in the potential window of 0 to 0.6 V vs Pt wire with scan rates of 0.1 V/s , 0.25 V/s , 0.5 V/s , 1 V/s and one linear sweep voltammogram in the potential window of 0 to 0.9 V vs Pt wire with a scan rate of 1 V/s were collected at each landing site of the SECCM capillary of the scan. Once the measurement on one spot was done, the capillary was retracted by $6 \mu\text{m}$ with a speed of $5 \mu\text{m/s}$ and moved to the next spot of the scan with lateral speed of $10 \mu\text{m/s}$. Several different scans were made with hopping distances of $7 \mu\text{m}$, $8 \mu\text{m}$, $9 \mu\text{m}$, $10 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure S5: Schematic illustration of the nanopipette approach toward the glassy carbon substrate. a) Coarse positioning of the nanopipette over the glassy carbon substrate with the aid of optical microscopy. b) Fine positioning of the double-barrel nanopipette using an alternating current signal. c) Approach curve recorded for one spot during SECCM measurements.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Section 5. Additional figures and tables

a) Potential conversion to RHE:

A carbon microelectrode is used to determine the half-wave potential of the used osmium complex. The preparation of such as carbon microelectrode was reported in earlier publications from the group.^[2] The half-wave potential of the sigmoidal curve obtained was used as a potential fix point (Figure S6). Because the SECCM landing on the particle displayed quasi-reversible Os complex voltammograms, the half-wave potential from the adjacent carbon landing spot neighbouring the particle landing spot was used to calculate the potential drift of the quasi-reference counter electrode for the particle landing spot. The voltammograms of the particle landing spot are then aligned by shifting the potential to account for the drift. After that voltammograms are converted to the RHE scale using $E_{\text{RHE}} = E_{\text{measured}} + E^{\circ}_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} + 0.059 \cdot \text{pH}$ with $E^{\circ}_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} = 0.210 \text{ V vs. NHE}$ for 3 M KCl solution at 25 °C.^[3]

Figure S6: Linear sweep voltammogram of 1 mM Os-complex in 0.05 M KOH solution

b) ECSA

$$ECSA = \frac{C_{DL}}{C_s}$$

where C_{DL} is electrochemical double layer capacitance and C_s is the specific capacitance. The specific capacitance was derived from the average of two top landing spot where particles had no cracks. The total capacitance value of all landing spots including the nearby carbon is obtained from the slope of the graph $(I_a - I_c)/2$ vs. scan rate, where I_a , I_c are the anodic and cathodic currents in the non-faradaic region (at 0.1 V), respectively (Figure S9). The C_{DL} of catalyst particles (Table S1) only was calculated by subtracting the average C_{DL} of the nearby carbon spot from the total C_{DL} obtained from the slope.

$$C_{DL}(\text{catalyst part}) = C_{DL}(\text{Total}) - \left[\frac{C_{DL}(\text{nearby carbon spot})}{GA \text{ of spot}} \times GA \text{ of carbon} \right]_{\text{average of nearby carbon spot}}$$

where GA is geometric area.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Figure S7: a) Selection of anodic and cathodic currents at 0.1 V from cyclic voltammograms of one of the spots at different scan rates. b) Plot of $(I_a - I_c)/2$ vs. scan rate for one of the spots. c) Plot of $(I_a - I_c)/2$ vs. scan rate for all spots.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Spot name	Electrochemical double layer capacitance C_{DL} (pA*s/V)	Electrochemical active surface area - ECSA (cm ²)	Geometric area of the spot (cm ²)	Geometric area of the carbon part (cm ²)
1	14.67	1.09×10^{-8}	1.18×10^{-8}	0
2	15.74	1.67×10^{-8}	1.09×10^{-8}	0
3	4.36	1.06×10^{-8}	0.93×10^{-8}	0
4	3.83	9.3×10^{-9}	0.91×10^{-8}	0
5	6.51	4.84×10^{-9}	1.30×10^{-8}	0.88×10^{-8}
6	4.06	9.87×10^{-9}	1.3×10^{-8}	0.76×10^{-8}
7	6.53	4.85×10^{-9}	1.37×10^{-8}	0.84×10^{-8}
8	5.69	4.23×10^{-9}	1.03×10^{-8}	0.66×10^{-8}
9	5.02	1.22×10^{-8}	1.25×10^{-8}	0
10	15.74	1.67×10^{-8}	1.09×10^{-8}	0
11	2.91	7.06×10^{-9}	0.6×10^{-8}	0

Table S1: Calculated electrochemical double layer capacitance, electrochemical active surface area, geometric area of spot and geometric area of carbon part in the spot for all the landing spots.

Figure S8. a) SEM micrographs of nanopipette landing spots on top of a particle (scale bar: 2 μm). b) Corresponding linear sweep voltammograms of the spots.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

c) AFM measurement:

The thickness of the particles was measured using AFM images. Due to residues of potassium hydroxide, there are artefacts in the images. Also, while moving the substrate from one place to another, some particles got moved which can be seen in the images.

Figure S9: AFM images of top spots on the particle used for thickness estimation

Figure S10: AFM images of edge landing spots on the particle used for thickness estimation

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

d) Ohmic resistance of the particles:

$$\Delta E = iR$$

where ΔE is the peak difference in the anodic peak position of the Os complex on the landing spots on the particle relative to the landing spots on the nearest neighbouring bare carbon, i is the current recorded and R is the resistance of the particle.

Figure S11: The change of peak potential as well as resistance with particle thickness for the top landing spots

e) Carbon current correction

$$I_{corrected} = I_{original} - A_{carbon+spot} \times J_{average\ of\ nearby\ carbon\ spot}$$

where $I_{corr.}$ is the current after subtraction of the carbon contribution, $I_{orig.}$ is the measured current, A is the geometric area of carbon in the edge landing spot, $J_{avg\ nearby\ carbon}$ is the average current density of the nearby carbon spots. The voltammograms of before and after correction of one of the spots are shown in Figure S7.

Figure S12. a) Linear sweep voltammograms of spots shown in Figure S9. b) Linear sweep voltammograms before and after carbon current correction.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

f) TOF calculations

$$TOF = \frac{j \times ECSA}{4 \times n \times F}$$

where j is current density at a specific potential, ECSA is the electrochemical surface area, 4 is the number of transferred electrons during OER, n is number of moles of Co atoms present at the particle, F is the Faraday constant.

The top of the particle consists of 1111 planes whereas edges of particle consist of 1110 plane. The number of Co atoms is calculated from the atom density for each plane as reported earlier.^[2] For 1111 facets, the atomic density for Co atoms is 3.5505×10^{18} atoms/cm², whereas for 1110 facets the density is 8.697×10^{18} Co atoms/cm². The geometric area of the landing spots was calculated to estimate the number of Co atom on both the facets which is used for TOF calculation. For the edge landing spot, the total current has contributions from both the planes. For estimating the TOF values of the 1111 plane and 1110 plane of the particle, the current contribution from both the facets had to be calculated. For calculation of $I_{top\ 111}$, the correlation of TOF values for landing spot 1-4 along with 11-14 (Figure S6) with particle thickness were established. Using the correlation equation (Figure S10) and particle thickness (Figure S10) for landing spot 5-10, the TOF values were calculated. From these TOF values obtained from the correlation equation, the current contribution from the top of the particles were calculated. By subtracting the $I_{top\ 111}$ from the total current, $I_{edge\ 110}$ was estimated. From these current values, TOF 1111 and TOF 1110 were calculated.

$$I_{total} = I_{top\ 111} + I_{edge\ 110}$$

$$I_{top\ 111} = TOF(\text{estimated from equation}) \times 4 \times n \times F$$

Or the modified equation for the above mentioned total current equation in terms of TOF is

$$TOF_{Total} = X_{top\ 111} * TOF_{Top\ 111} + X_{Edge\ 110} * TOF_{Edge\ 110}$$

Where X_{top} (fraction of top 111 Co atoms) = n_{top}/n_{total} , X_{edge} (fraction of edge 110 Co atoms) = n_{edge}/n_{total}

Equation used to calculate the TOF values for estimating $I_{top\ 111}$ are:

$$y = -164.55x + 78.112 \text{ for } 1.8 \text{ V vs. RHE (Figure 2c)}$$

where x , y represents the TOF and thickness of particle.

References

- [1] I. Menapace, W. Yiming, E. Masad, *Fuel* **2017**, *202*, 366–379.
 [2] T. Quast, H. B. Aiyappa, S. Saddeler, P. Wilde, Y.-T. Chen, S. Schulz, W. Schuhmann, *Angew. Chem. Int. ed.* **2021**, *60*, 3576–3580.
 [3] T. Tarnev, H. B. Aiyappa, A. Botz, T. Erichsen, A. Ernst, C. Andronesco, W. Schuhmann, *Angew. Chem. Int. ed.* **2019**, *58*, 14265–14269.

Author Contributions

S. Varhade: Data collection (equal), data interpretation (equal), writing of initial draft (lead)
 E. Batsa Tetteh: Data interpretation (supporting), writing of manuscript (supporting)
 S. Saddeler: Data collection (supporting), data interpretation (supporting)
 S. Schumacher: Data interpretation (supporting)
 H. Barike Aiyappa: Data interpretation (supporting)
 G. Bendt: Data collection (supporting), data interpretation (supporting)
 S. Schulz: Project administration (equal), funding acquisition (equal), data interpretation (equal)
 C. Andronesco: Research idea and concept (supporting), administration (equal), funding acquisition (equal), data interpretation (equal), writing of manuscript (supporting)
 W. Schuhmann: Research idea and concept (lead), project administration (equal), funding acquisition (equal), data interpretation (equal), writing of manuscript (supporting)